

More on the garden orb-web spider *Argiope australis* (Walckenaer, 1805) in South Africa (Araneae: Araneidae)

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Abstract: This paper provides information on the garden orb-web spider *Argiope australis* as observed in the Free State, South Africa. A large number of the specimens have been photographed. Information on their somatic variation, behaviour and distribution is provided.

Key words: South African National Survey of Arachnida, Free State, predation.

INTRODUCTION

Members of the genus *Argiope* Audouin, 1826 with their large size and bright colouration were some of the first tropical spiders to be described (*Araneoides capensis* Petiver, 1702).

Several species with lobed abdomens of the genus *Argiope* are known from the Afrotropical Region. However, there seems to be large variability in morphological features of these species, as well as their genitalia (Levi, 1983; Bjørn, 1997; Jäger, 2020). Due to this variation, Kolosvary (1938) argues that all lobed *Argiope* in Africa should be considered subspecies of *A. lobata* (Pallas, 1772), the type species of the genus. This variability makes species identification problematic, as can be seen in the >80 *Argiope* synonyms presently listed in the World Spider Catalog (2022).

As part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa), surveys were undertaken over a wide area and numerous *Argiope* specimens were collected, as well as photographs taken. Observations on several species were made during a 14-year survey in a grassland fragment at Mpetsane Conservation Estate (MCE) in the Free State province, South Africa. *Argiope* species were some of the spiders closely monitored. Two species of lobed *Argiope* have been reported from the MCE: *A. australis* (Walckenaer, 1805) and *A. lobata* (Jones & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2021). However, on closer inspection of the genitalia, we found that there are only two species of lobed *Argiope* in the MCE, namely *A. australis*, but large variations in body shape and colour were found.

In this paper, we provide information on *A. australis* observed in the field over a period of several years. A large number of the specimens have been observed and photographed. Information on their somatic variation is provided, as well as information on their behaviour and distribution.

METHOD

The survey was carried out in grassland at the MCE, which is situated in the Eastern Free State highlands some 14 km from Clocolan. The MCE (28°48'S; 27°39'E) covers 164 ha and is a registered conservancy (Amohela-ho-Spitskop) sanctuary and nature reserve. The estate is on average 1 700 m above sea level, with an annual rainfall of 720 mm. More than 1 000 photographs were taken of *Argiope* specimens and their webs at MCE. The photographs and observations were made by the second author (AJ). While staying on the reserve, he was able to regularly walk in the field to photograph spiders and make observations.

Figure 1. *Argiope australis* female in web at MCE. Photo credit Allen Jones

TAXONOMY

Argiope australis is an African endemic species described as *Epeira australis* from the Cape of Good Hope, South Africa and Ile de France (Mauritius), but no type material remains in existence. In order to obtain nomenclatural and taxonomical stability, Bjørn (1997) designated a female neotype herein from Zaire: Katanga, Kasapa (11°35'S 27°25'E).

In the revision of the African *Argiope* species, Bjørn (1997) examined all available material from 13 museums. This included 80 lobed *Argiope* specimens from the National Collection of Arachnida, South Africa. He recognised two species from South Africa: *A. lobata* and *A. australis*; however, the majority of specimens (76) belong to *A. australis* and only three were identified as *A. lobata* (Bjørn, 1997).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION

Argiope australis is recorded throughout the eastern part of Africa, from Sudan through South Africa, in the eastern part of Zaïre, as well as from Senegal and Angola.

Diagnostic characteristics: TL female 24-30 mm, male 5-7 mm. **Female:** Carapace with reflecting hairs; ocular area dark; thorax with sides more parallel; sternum with median pale patch (Fig. 1). Abdomen without shoulders, with bluntly rounded lateral lobes; sometimes with posterior tail; dorsal pattern consisting of 3-5 transverse bands that are variable (Fig. 2); ventrally with median dark band bordered by series of yellow spots (Fig. 4b); in juveniles bands sometimes yellow and more orange-red. Legs banded. Epigyne: Shape of epigynal roof is highly variable (Figs 3c-d), but roof always somewhat narrowed.

Variation: The colour of the abdomen varies from pale yellow, almost creamy (Fig. 2h), to a bright yellow (Fig. 2b); the transverse bands vary from dark and uninterrupted (Figs 2c-d, 2g) to faint (Figs 2a-b); interrupted (Fig. 2e); black to red (Fig. 2f) or black with reddish tint (Figs 2h-i).

Male: Carapace light brown with longitudinal darker brown band on each side of the fovea; ocular region with dark rings around eyes; thorax with almost parallel sides (Figs 4a-b). Coxae and trochanters light brown, legs light brown with darker spots. Abdominal dorsal pattern consisting of two longitudinal brown lines on white background; ventral pattern consisting of two paraxial white lines bordering greyish median area. Palp: The shape of the embolus thorn can vary to a large extent, ranging from merely acute through broad and spade like. The length of the thorn, however, is always longer (Figs 4c-d) than the width of the embolus just distal to the insertion of the thorn.

Figure 2. Abdomens of *Argiope australis* females taken at MCE showing the variation. Photo credit Allen Jones.

Figure 4. *Argiope australis*: a-b. Female's ventral view with male dorsal view; . Photo credit Rudi Steenkamp

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA

The species is very commonly found in South Africa (Fig. 5). It was sampled from all the floral biomes in South Africa such as the Grassland (Haddad *et al.*, 2013) and Savanna (Foord *et al.*, 2011). It was also collected from crops such as avocado, peach and pistachio orchards, pine plantations and pumpkin fields (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2013). In the past, they were frequently found in gardens – hence the common name.

Figure 3. *Argiope australis* females: a. Habitus after Bjørn (1997); b. Epigyne variation after Bjørn (1997); c-d. Epigyne variation. Photo credit Allen

Figure 5. *Argiope australis*: a. Female in web, ventral view with male; b. Male palp lateral view; c. Male palp after Bjørn (1997) Photo credit 5a Allen Jones

COMMON NAME

In South Africa, *A. australis* is known by several common names, such as butter spider, pumpkin spider, black and yellow banded spider or garden orb-web spiders.

CONSERVATION MEASURES

Argiope australis has been sampled from more than 30 protected areas, including national parks and reserves in all the provinces such as Polokwane Nature Reserve (Dippenaar *et al.*, 2008), Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad *et al.*, 2006) and Addo Elephant National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2020). No conservation actions are recommended. Due to its wide distribution, it is listed as Least Concern.

BEHAVIOUR

Web: They typically spin a large orb-web 400-600 mm in diameter between strong grass stalks or even other plant stalks (Fig. 6). Generally built in open grassland, usually between tall stalks and low shrubs. The webs are dense with many radii, making it strong and it is well anchored. The webs are no more than 300-400 mm above ground. However, there is a record of a web built on top of a wild asparagus bush about 2 m high, a web that was used constantly for 62 days. They are present on the web day and night, even in frosty days and misty mornings. The spider hangs in the centre of the web, head facing downwards. They often use the same web for long periods, and periodical repairs are made when damage occurs (Fig. 7). The males were in their own webs and only a few were found in females' webs. The males are found around the margins of the web during the mating season, which is usually in summer (Fig. 5a).

Immature spiders (8-10 mm) make complete orb-webs, 200 mm above ground level. The web is a perfect miniature of the adult web and is about 180 mm in diameter. The adult females often make webs that are inclined to between 30-40 degrees or more from the vertical. This is clearly intended since the web does not sag. The strand tensions are perfectly designed to compensate for a spider with prey and to allow for wind effect, which will cause the whole web to ripple but not break.

Stabilimentum: They do not always make a stabilimentum in the web and webs have often been observed without one. The stabilimenta in webs are not very dense and can vary from a central strip stretching upwards or downwards (Figs 5a, 6-7).

Prey: The symmetrical orb-webs are clearly visible yet the spiders are extremely successful at catching a variety of prey such as butterflies, bees, flies, grasshoppers and even the occasional dragonfly. The prey is wrapped in silk through rapid movements of the hind legs, and is eaten when safely secured. After some rain at MCE, an "Argiope city" was discovered where 50-60 *Argiope* spider webs were present in the bushes. It was not common to find so many spiders present just in this one location on the farm, as they are normally found throughout the estate. The spiders were probably attracted to the high numbers of grasshoppers [Orthoptera Acrididae, *Truxalis* sp.] that were found in most webs (Fig. 8) (Jones, 2012).

Figure 6. *Argiope australis* female in new orb web. Photo credit Allen Jones

Figure 7. *Argiope australis* female in old orb web showing damage due to wind. Photo credit Allen Jones

Figure 8. *Argiope australis* female feeding on grasshoppers (Orthoptera Acrididae, *Truxalis* sp.) Photo credit Allen Jones

Predators: On several occasions dead spiders have been found killed by fiscal shrikes (*Lanius collaris*), also known as Jan Fiskaal, fiskaallaksman or “Jackie Hanger” (Fig. 9).

Figure 9. *Argiope australis* killed by fiscal shrikes (*Lanius collaris*). Photo credit Allen Jones

Spiders relocate frequently and they have a perfect sense for a new successful food source, and frequently congregate in numbers at an abundant site; clearly there is close communication among them. A female was photographed that had abandoned her web and embarked upon an epic journey, being such large heavy creatures they cannot balloon. She walked clambering over plants and grass leaves, occasionally stopping to rest. One female covered 3 m in 5 minutes of arduous effort. All the while she was exposed and totally vulnerable. She cannot feed along the way. New web sites are generally several hundred metres away. When she does arrive at a suitable site, she begins the process of creating a new web.

Figure 10. *Argiope australis* “walking” over grass to find a new web site. Photo credit Allen Jones

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